

ISCB Bioinformatics Competency Framework - Bioinformatics core facility scientists profiles

This form will collect your opinions on the proficiency levels that different core facility scientists would require for the bioinformatics competencies listed in the ISCB's Framework

* Indicates required question

Name (Please note that this question is optional and that no personal information will be shared with third parties)

Your answer

What is your current role? *

Your answer

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

Is this a leadership/managerial role? *

Yes

No

Other:

Please briefly describe your current responsibilities within your role

Your answer

What is your institution?

Your answer

Which is your country of employment?

Your answer

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

Email address

Your answer

Description

The ISCB competency framework is a minimum information standard defining the competencies required, and the levels they're required at, for bioinformatics professionals, being one of them a 'Bioinformatics core facility scientist.

As this profile does not reflect career progression, a Bioinformatics Core Facility Scientists Competencies Taskforce was created on July 2023 at the ISCB's Bioinfo-Core Meeting.

Three professional profiles for scientists in bioinformatics core facilities were proposed for reflecting career progression. In addition, a managerial role is also define for professionals whose main responsibility is management.

- Core facility scientist I
- Core facility scientist II
- Core facility scientist III
- A managerial role

The current version of the ISCB Bioinformatics Competency Framework already has 13 competencies. In order describe the activities for a core facility scientist profile more accurately the task force added six more competencies. You will find the full list of competencies in the questions below. If you want to find a full description of the competencies, and the knowledge, skills and attitudes included in each of them, check [this document](#).

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

Your Input

Now that the Core Facility Scientists Competencies Taskforce has identified a set of Profiles, Competencies, Knowledge, Skills and Attitudes, we are asking professionals within the bioinformatics core facilities communities to identify up to what extent people within the four profiles need to manage each of the competencies. You will be using a three level scale to evaluate this.

- Level 1: Knowledge/Comprehension - remembering previously learned information and/or grasping the meaning of information
- Level 2: Application/Analysis - applying knowledge to actual situations and/or breaking down objects or ideas into simpler parts and seeing how the parts relate and are organised
- Level 3: Synthesis/Evaluation - rearranging component ideas into a new whole and/or making judgments based on internal evidence or external criteria

Please click on next to start your evaluation.

Profile: Core facility scientist I

Please input the proficiency levels you deem necessary so that an 'Entry level' bioinformatics core facility scientist can do their work

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

Levels

- Level 1: Knowledge/Comprehension - remembering previously learned information and/or grasping the meaning of information
- Level 2: Application/Analysis - applying knowledge to actual situations and/or breaking down objects or ideas into simpler parts and seeing how the parts relate and are organised
- Level 3: Synthesis/Evaluation - rearranging component ideas into a new whole and/or making judgments based on internal evidence or external criteria

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

Profile: Core facility scientist I *

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3 (most advanced)	Not Applicable
A3: Work at depth in at least one technical area aligned with the life sciences	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
B3: Prepare life science data for computational analysis	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
C3: Have a positive impact on scientific discovery through bioinformatics	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
D3: Use data science methods suitable for the size and complexity of the data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
E3: Manage own and others' data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

principles

F3: Make appropriate use of bioinformatics tools and resources

G3: Contribute effectively to the design and development of user-centric bioinformatics tools and resources

H3: Make appropriate and efficient use of scripting and programming languages

I3: Construct, manage and maintain bioinformatics computing infrastructure of varying complexity

J3: Comply with professional

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

and codes of

conduct relevant
to computational
biology

K3:
Communicate
meaningfully with
a range of
audiences -
within and
beyond your
profession

L3: Work
effectively in
teams to
accomplish a
common goal

M3: Engage in
continuing
professional
development in
bioinformatics

New: Identify and
support users'
needs

New: Project
management

New: People
management

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

New:
Collaborator
engagement

New: Training

New: Leadership

New: Leadership

Profile: Core facility scientist II

Please input the proficiency levels you deem necessary so that an 'Mid level' bioinformatics core facility scientist can do their work

Levels

- Level 1: Knowledge/Comprehension - remembering previously learned information and/or grasping the meaning of information
- Level 2: Application/Analysis - applying knowledge to actual situations and/or breaking down objects or ideas into simpler parts and seeing how the parts relate and are organised
- Level 3: Synthesis/Evaluation - rearranging component ideas into a new whole and/or making judgments based on internal evidence or external criteria

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

Profile: Core facility scientist II *

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3 (most advanced)	Not Applicable
A3: Work at depth in at least one technical area aligned with the life sciences	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
B3: Prepare life science data for computational analysis	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
C3: Have a positive impact on scientific discovery through bioinformatics	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
D3: Use data science methods suitable for the size and complexity of the data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
E3: Manage own and others' data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

principles

F3: Make appropriate use of bioinformatics tools and resources

G3: Contribute effectively to the design and development of user-centric bioinformatics tools and resources

H3: Make appropriate and efficient use of scripting and programming languages

I3: Construct, manage and maintain bioinformatics computing infrastructure of varying complexity

J3: Comply with professional

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

and codes of

conduct relevant
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K3:
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meaningfully with
a range of
audiences -
within and
beyond your
profession

L3: Work
effectively in
teams to
accomplish a
common goal

M3: Engage in
continuing
professional
development in
bioinformatics

New: Identify and
support users'
needs

New: Project
management

New: People
management

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

New:
Collaborator
engagement

New: Training

New: Leadership

New: Leadership

Profile: Core facility scientist III

Please input the proficiency levels you deem necessary so that an 'Higher level' bioinformatics core facility scientist can do their work

Levels

- Level 1: Knowledge/Comprehension - remembering previously learned information and/or grasping the meaning of information
- Level 2: Application/Analysis - applying knowledge to actual situations and/or breaking down objects or ideas into simpler parts and seeing how the parts relate and are organised
- Level 3: Synthesis/Evaluation - rearranging component ideas into a new whole and/or making judgments based on internal evidence or external criteria

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

Profile: Core facility scientist III *

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3 (most advanced)	Not Applicable
A3: Work at depth in at least one technical area aligned with the life sciences	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
B3: Prepare life science data for computational analysis	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
C3: Have a positive impact on scientific discovery through bioinformatics	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
D3: Use data science methods suitable for the size and complexity of the data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
E3: Manage own and others' data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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principles

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profession

L3: Work
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teams to
accomplish a
common goal

M3: Engage in
continuing
professional
development in
bioinformatics

New: Identify and
support users'
needs

New: Project
management

New: People
management

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

New:
Collaborator
engagement

New: Training

New: Leadership

New: Leadership

Managerial role

Please input the proficiency levels you deem necessary so that a lead (or manager) of a bioinformatics core facility can do their work

Levels

- Level 1: Knowledge/Comprehension - remembering previously learned information and/or grasping the meaning of information
- Level 2: Application/Analysis - applying knowledge to actual situations and/or breaking down objects or ideas into simpler parts and seeing how the parts relate and are organised
- Level 3: Synthesis/Evaluation - rearranging component ideas into a new whole and/or making judgments based on internal evidence or external criteria

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

Managerial role *

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3 (most advanced)	Not Applicable
A3: Work at depth in at least one technical area aligned with the life sciences	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
B3: Prepare life science data for computational analysis	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
C3: Have a positive impact on scientific discovery through bioinformatics	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
D3: Use data science methods suitable for the size and complexity of the data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
E3: Manage own and others' data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

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L3: Work
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M3: Engage in
continuing
professional
development in
bioinformatics

New: Identify and
support users'
needs

New: Project
management

New: People
management

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

New:
Collaborator
engagement

New: Training

New: Leadership

New: Leadership

Additional information

Do you have any observations or comments about the profiles, competencies or the scales used for the evaluation of the profiles?

Your answer

Thank you for your participation in this evaluation!!

If you want more information about this project please access the [project's page](#) or join the [ISCB's Bioinfo-Core community](#).

Get link

Pre-fill responses, then click 'Get link'

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